

Time Dependent Drone-aided Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Windows and Multi-visits

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Abstract

The continuous development of e-commerce and ongoing pandemic in recent years leads to a large increase in the demand for last-mile delivery with higher standards of service quality. The usage of unmanned aerial vehicles, also known as drones, is an ideal solution for such complex delivery problems. When designing the delivery system with the drone, we cannot omit the following features of drones: drones have the unique ability to avoid traffic congestion compared to truck traveling; and the dispatched drones need customer assistance to retrieve goods in parcel releasing procedures. In this paper, the time-dependent vehicle routing problem with drones and time windows (TDVRPDTW) is introduced. For practical application scenarios, the parcel releasing operation of drones needs customer assistance. Thus, the drone visits are fulfilled in given time windows for each demand point. Besides, the time-dependent traveling routes of trucks are also considered to capture road congestion. The objective is to minimize total route makespan, and vehicles' dispatch times at the depot are crucial to avoid urban congestion. We present a branch-and-price algorithm to solve the optimization. The master problem is solved using a customized column generation algorithm and the pricing problem is solved by a tailored labeling algorithm with a novel dominance rule that allows more label dominance. For our numerous experimental results, we modified Solomon's data sets by adding time dependency. Our algorithm can solve all the small-scale and medium-scale instances optimally. In terms of large-size instances, more than 90% are solved optimally within 2 hours.

Key words: Time-dependent travel times, Time window, Vehicle routing problem with drones, Branch-and-price, Last-mile delivery, Integer programming

1. Introduction

Special features of drones have been studied in both academia and industry in recent years. Compared to truck delivery, drone delivery is faster, cheaper, more flexible, and can reduce CO₂ emissions for the environment's sake. Therefore, an increasing number of industrial delivery processes try to explore the potential of drones in last-mile delivery. The last mile is defined as the transit of packages from a transportation hub to a final destination in supply chain management and transportation planning. The drone delivery mode can potentially bring cost-benefit and better service quality for the last-mile delivery. In this way, customers can enjoy more convenient and timely service.

However, there may be restrictions when using drones for deliveries. Flight range, payload restrictions, infrastructure that is densely populated, stringent regulations governing the use of urban airspace, and weather are some of the known operational limits of delivery drones. It is essential to take drone features into account and evaluate operating variables when planning an operation. Otherwise, a choice can lead to either an overestimation or an underestimation of the capital requirements.

Drone cooperation with truck delivery has therefore raised more attention. Traditional last-mile deliveries performed by trucks are modeled as a vehicle routing problem (VRP), which has been extensively studied in literature. The research on drone-related routing problems can be traced back to flying sidekick traveling salesman problem, which was the first paper to outline the scenario of deploying both a delivery truck and a drone together for package delivery in logistics distribution, and a greedy construction heuristic algorithm is developed to solve the problem [Murray & Chu \(2015\)](#). Thereafter, a large amount of works regarding different variants and problems with different features are conducted. In [Choi & Schonfeld \(2017\)](#), the vehicle routing problem with drones (VRPD) is proposed when multiple trucks and drones are involved.

From the truck transportation point of view, time-dependent traveling time on edges is an important consideration for the more practical truck-drone delivery system. The travel time between two customers or between a customer and the depot not only depends on the distance between the points but also the departure time of day. This induces restrictions for truck delivery with

1 time-dependent speed is given route conditions. For instance, in [Chen et al. \(2006\)](#), the time-
2 dependent vehicle routing problem extends the VRP to account for urban congestion. Similarly,
3 the time-dependent traveling salesman problem is an extension of the traveling salesman problem
4 (TSP). The VRP assumes that the price or duration of the trip between two places is well-known and
5 consistent. Most of the time, the VRP assumes that the costs or trip times are scalar transformations
6 of distances. It is possible to employ a composite or modified measure of cost for practical purposes.

7 Regarding the time window constraint for delivery stemming from the customer available time
8 slots of receiving parcels, previous works mainly attach such constraints on trucks. Nevertheless, as
9 nowadays truck may only deliver goods to transfer hubs or delivery lockers, disregarding customers'
10 available time, drones are the main medium that directly contact with receivers. Therefore, the
11 work on truck-drone delivery system with time window imposed for drones remains scarce. In
12 real-world applications, the time window for customer receiving goods is a restriction for drone
13 delivery because drones need manual help to retrieve and launch from the customer location.

14 Similar to the time windows associated with vehicle routing problems (VRPTW), conceptually
15 each customer may demand a certain amount of goods and specifies a time window that indicates
16 when drone delivery can take place. In [Desrochers et al. \(1992\)](#), the objective is to determine a
17 set of routes that minimize the total travel cost while ensuring that all customers are served. Time
18 windows are respected, and the capacity limit of the vehicles is not violated. It is assumed that all
19 vehicles start and end their routes at a common depot and that travel cost and travel time between
20 each pair of locations in the problem are known. As stated in [Fu et al. \(2008\)](#), time windows for
21 serving the clients may also be expressed as the maximum permitted duration of each route, i.e., the
22 driver's workday. As for the constraints on the drone delivery time window, the settings are similar.

23 Concerning the algorithms to solve VRPTW and time-dependent vehicle routing problems with
24 time windows (TDVRPTW), exact solution methods and heuristic methods are mainly contained.
25 The TDVRPTW is optimally solved in [Dabia et al. \(2013\)](#) using a branch-and-price method. In a
26 branch-and-price method, column generation is used to solve the linear relaxation in each branch-
27 and-bound node. It is challenging to find a solution due to the vehicle's mobility and synchrony
28 as a mobile battery switching station. Although various effective meta-heuristics and accurate
29 algorithms have been devised to solve the VRPTW, methods made to cope with the TDVRPTW, let

1 alone the unique TDVRPDTW, are mostly heuristic in nature. Therefore, it is essential to consider
2 exact methods for increased performance. In this paper, we apply the branch-and-price algorithm
3 with a tailored labeling approach in the column generation process to solve the problem.

4 To address the above issues, in this paper we propose a novel variant of the vehicle routing
5 problem with drones, in which the truck-drone delivery system combines both time windows for
6 customer service and time-dependent edge traveling duration. The objective is to minimize the
7 total makespan of all vehicles, including the travel times between vehicle nodes and the waiting
8 times incurred by drones returning to vehicle nodes. Optimal decisions are made at the depot and
9 multi-visit drones are allowed. The proposed model formulation considers not only the basics of the
10 truck-drone delivery scenario but also the representation concerning time-dependent traveling time
11 for vehicle routes and the time window for drone delivery. In the proposed branch-and-price exact
12 method, when considering time-dependent travel times, standard dominance tests taken directly
13 from the VRPTW become time-consuming and weak. In this paper, we introduce new dominance
14 criteria by exploiting the structure of the problem. The performance of the branch-and-price
15 algorithm is verified on newly generated instances extended from the Solomon benchmark proposed
16 in [Solomon \(1987\)](#). Small-scale instances are solvable directly using off-the-shelf solvers, and
17 the established exact algorithm shows better performance than solver results for medium-scale
18 instances. The main contributions of this paper are:

- 19 1. Introduce a new variant of the VRPD, where time-dependent traveling routes for vehicles
20 and time windows for drone delivery are considered. And practical constraints, for instance,
21 drones' endurance modeling are considered.
- 22 2. Construct a mixed-integer programming (MIP) model for the TDVRPDTW problem, com-
23 prised of the truck-drone delivery system, drone multi-visit properties, as well as the synchro-
24 nization of truck-drone pairs. A specialized linearization method is adopted to derive the
25 piecewise linear drone battery energy consumption to make the problem as mixed-integer
26 linear programming (MILP).
- 27 3. Present a branch-and-price algorithm to determine the set of routes that minimizes the sum
28 of the total makespan of all routes. The pricing problem that arises is solved by a tailored

1 labeling algorithm and accelerated by machine learning techniques. Duly apply numerical
2 tests based on benchmark instances to evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm
3 and the value of drone allocation decisions.

4 **2. Related Works**

5 This review focuses on comprehensive literature regarding the previous works on time-dependent
6 vehicle routing problems with time windows, the drone-aided delivery system with multi-visits
7 extension in drone flight, and algorithms for solving time-dependent VRP with time windows.

8 *2.1. Time-dependent Vehicle Routing Problem with Time Window*

9 This section reviews relevant literature concerning vehicle routing problems constrained under
10 time-dependent vehicle routes and customer time windows for receiving goods. The traveling
11 salesman problem (TSP) and vehicle routing problem (VRP) with time windows are examined by
12 [Zhao et al. \(2019\)](#). In [Zhou et al.](#), several types of vehicle routing problems with time windows are
13 surveyed.

14 From the practical relevance perspective, the vehicle routing problem with time windows
15 (VRPTW) is extensively studied in the literature. Consequently, many heuristics and exact methods
16 are successfully developed to solve this problem. However, the majority of the models now in use
17 are time-independent, meaning that the amount of time required to travel between any two points is
18 taken to be constant and regardless of the time of day. This assumption is untrue due to the day-
19 to-day variations in traffic congestion. It is obvious that solutions to the VRPTW developed from
20 time-independent models could be impossible to execute in practice. There are significant delays as
21 a result of traffic congestion. However, these delays are anticipated for numerous routes. Therefore,
22 while dealing with the VRPTW, addressing time-dependent journey periods may substantially
23 assure feasibility.

24 With continuous development in drone delivery, [Chen et al. \(2021b\)](#) and [Chen et al. \(2021a\)](#)
25 provide a VRP that is a variation of the vehicle routing issue with drones that includes time windows
26 and delivery robots (VRPD). When a vehicle stops at a spot, they believe each robot can only
27 deliver once while transporting a single item. Additionally, a two-stage metaheuristic algorithm

1 and an adaptable large neighborhood search approach are created. The two-echelon vehicle routing
2 issue with time windows and mobile satellites is introduced in Ref. [Li et al. \(2020\)](#). Deliveries are
3 made via a uniform fleet of truck-drone combinations. In their issue, there are three different sorts
4 of pathways. The first is referred to as the pure drone route since the route starts and finishes at the
5 depot and is completed by a drone without the aid of a vehicle. The second is known as the pure
6 truck route, in which the truck goes without the aid of drones. The third type of route is referred to
7 as a combined route, in which packages are delivered using both a vehicle and a drone.

8 Apart from the time window constraints, the following works feature additional time-dependent
9 truck travel time. The time-dependent vehicle routing problem (TDVRP) is defined as follows.
10 From a central depot, a fleet of fixed-capacity vehicles must serve clients with fixed requests. To
11 reduce the overall time spent on the routes, customers are assigned to certain trucks, which are then
12 routed. A specific instance of the TDVRP known as the time-dependent traveling salesman problem
13 (TDTSP) arises when there is only one vehicle with limitless capacity [Malandraki & Daskin \(1992\)](#).

14 The TSP is examined in Ref. [Emambocus et al. \(2021\)](#) with costs assigned to each node
15 dependent on both its location in the sequence and the node that comes before it. Numerous papers
16 on the subject of vehicle routing problems assume a time-independent environment, in which the
17 amount of time required to travel a connection between any two sites is unrelated to the time of
18 departure. More researchers have shifted their focus to the optimization of the time-dependent
19 vehicle routing issues as a result of the realization that vehicles operate in a stochastic and dynamic
20 environment [Laporte \(1992\)](#); [Toth & Vigo \(2002\)](#); [Laporte \(2007\)](#). The prior time-dependent TSP
21 is given a new formulation about [Miranda-Bront et al. \(2010\)](#). They presumptively believe that any
22 two cities may be reached in one time period and that the expense of traveling between them varies
23 with the length of time.

24 *2.2. Drone-aided Delivery System with Multi-visits Extension in Drone Flight*

25 This section reviews relevant literature where drones are allowed to visit one or multiple
26 customers during a single flight for vehicle routing problems with drones. The major uses of many
27 visits per drone journey have been in surveillance ([Campbell et al., 2018](#)) or reconnaissance ([Luo
28 et al., 2017, 2018](#); [Liu et al., 2019](#)). The choice has not been expanded to include the combined

1 truck-drone routing challenge in many works.

2 The representative works are as follows. The VRPD, which enables drones to make numerous
3 deliveries per trip and return to any available truck in the fleet or a docking station, was researched
4 by [Wang & Sheu \(2019\)](#). The maximum flight time and maximum weight that a drone may carry
5 place restrictions on the drone path. The two-echelon vehicle routing problem with drones with
6 many visits and several drones per truck was developed by [Kitjacharoenchai et al. \(2020\)](#), which
7 enforces a drone flight endurance model based on the maximum length of a drone route. The
8 k -multi-visit drone routing issue, which takes into account a tandem between a truck and k drones
9 to enable a drone to deliver one or more products to clients, was proposed by [Poikonen & Golden](#)
10 [\(2020\)](#). The energy consumption rate, which is chosen based on the projections in [Stolaroff et al.](#)
11 [\(2018\)](#), is pertinent to the cargo and the trip distance. In a unique scenario, the truck is required
12 to always go from the launch location to the recovery point immediately following the launch of
13 any drones. This poses a synchronization challenge between the truck and k drones. A multi-drop
14 truck-drone team logistics issue was developed by [Gonzalez-R et al. \(2020\)](#), which enables the
15 drone to deliver many packages in a single trip. For simplicity, it is assumed that the drone's energy
16 consumption pattern is linear and only dependent on distance.

17 *2.3. Algorithms for Solving Time-dependent VRP with Time Window*

18 The majority of publications deal with the VRPTW based on meta-heuristics and few addresses
19 the inherent time-dependent nature of time-dependent vehicle routing problems with time windows
20 (TDVRPTW) using exact approaches. In [Lübbecke & Desrosiers \(2005\)](#), column generation was
21 successfully implemented for the VRPTW. And an overview of column generation algorithms is
22 surveyed.

23 It is noteworthy that the column generation method of [Dabia et al. \(2013\)](#) took the dispatch
24 time from the depot into account as a decision variable but presupposed time-independent journey
25 timings. In addition to solving the price subproblem's shortest path problem, Ref. [Ioachim et al.](#)
26 [\(1998\)](#) also does such. They also must specify a sufficient dominance criterion and store complicated
27 functions in each label. In [Dabia et al. \(2019\)](#), the objective is to minimize the summation of
28 vehicles' fixed costs and routing costs. The timing of routes is crucial since starting the service at

1 the client has an impact on the cost, i.e., fines apply if the service starts outside of the time slots,
2 according to the work of [Liberatore et al. \(2011\)](#). The authors address difficulties that are connected
3 to those in this work to address this price challenge. The assumption of time-independent transit
4 times remains, nevertheless.

5 The goal of [Savelsbergh \(1992\)](#) is to reduce overall route duration. The following are the
6 justifications for choosing the objective function. First, the literature on time-dependent routing
7 usually makes use of a comparable goal function. From a practical standpoint, route duration
8 reduction is crucial. Cutting the length of the trip can save pay costs and make it simpler to adhere
9 to driving time restrictions. Although the master problem of the column generation approach is
10 the same in [Dabia et al. \(2013\)](#), the pricing problem is more challenging than it is in the VRPTW
11 because time dependency is implicitly incorporated into the set of feasible routes, making it a
12 time-dependent elementary shortest path problem with resource constraints. Along with the time-
13 dependent trip durations, the goal is also a reduction of the overall duration of all routes. Due to the
14 first-in-first-out (FIFO) assumption, [Tilk et al. \(2017\)](#), the pricing problem may be represented with
15 nondecreasing resource extension functions if the conventional VRPTW aim of reducing the total
16 cost of arcs included in the solution was maintained.

17 The methods to include the time-varying constraints into programming formulation lie in the
18 following works. Due to the time dependency, the dispatch timings of the trucks at the depot are
19 critical in [Haghani & Jung \(2005\)](#). In reality, because congestion may be avoided, a later dispatch
20 time at the depot might lead to a shorter journey time. It is determined which set of routes reduces
21 the total route duration. The order in which clients are visited throughout the routes determines the
22 dispatch schedules for the trucks at the depot. In [Melgarejo et al. \(2015\)](#), the congested roads are
23 considered by assuming time-dependent travel times: a different trip time is incurred based on the
24 departure time at a place. Each of the time zones that make up the planning horizon is linked with
25 a distinct pace. The resultant stepwise speed function is converted into non-overtaking trip time
26 functions. Such trip time functions adhere to the FIFO principle.

27 Concerning the algorithms based on tabu search in [Malandraki & Daskin \(1992\)](#), there are
28 various strategies offered for both the TDVRP and the time-dependent traveling salesman problem,
29 as well as mixed-integer linear formulations for the TDVRP. A local search algorithm for the

1 TDVRPTW is created in Hashimoto et al. (2008), and a dynamic programming algorithm is
 2 included in the local search to find the ideal start time for each route. Haghani & Jung (2005)
 3 presents a genetic algorithm; Donati et al. (2008) and Balseiro et al. (2011) offer algorithms
 4 based on an ant colony system. Tang et al. (2008) highlights the challenge of adopting route
 5 improvement processes when journey durations are time-dependent and suggests effective solutions
 6 to the problem. A restricted dynamic programming approach is presented in Ref. Malandraki &
 7 Dial (1996) for the time-dependent traveling salesman issue. Only a subset with a predetermined
 8 size and made up of the best answers is preserved after each iteration of the dynamic programming
 9 method and utilized to calculate solutions in the following iteration. Referring to Zografos et al.
 10 (2009), they offer a method based on breaking down the multi-criteria routing issue into a series of
 11 simpler itinerary subproblems that are then resolved using dynamic programming.

12 3. Problem Statement and Mathematical Model

13 This section provides a formal description and a MILP formulation of the TDVRPDTW problem.

14 3.1. Problem Definition

15 We first provide in Fig. 1 the schematic layout for a TDVRPDTW solution example with 11
 16 clients and 2 truck-drone pairs to better clarify the issue situation. Information on client assignments
 17 to the truck and drones, the order in which the truck and drones visit customers, and the launch
 18 and retrieval nodes for each drone journey is all part of the problem's solution. Customers may
 19 be represented as nodes in the solution's directed acyclic graph, and directed arcs can be used to
 20 represent the precedence ordering of visits by the truck or the drone.

21 The routes for the fleet's trucks are $0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 0$ (truck 1), and $0 \rightarrow 3 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 6 \rightarrow$
 22 $7 \rightarrow 0$ (truck 2), each represented by a solid directed line. Routes for the drone attached to truck 1
 23 are shown by red dotted lines. Drone 1 initially serves client node 8 during time intervals $[e_8, l_8]$
 24 after leaving the depot before synchronizing with truck 1 at node 1. Then, during time slots $[e_{10}, l_{10}]$,
 25 drone 1 travels to node 10 from node 2 and then makes a direct return to the depot. Similar to drone
 26 1, drone 2 departs truck 2 at node 3 to deliver packages to nodes 9 and 11 within time periods $[e_9, l_9]$

Figure 1: Trajectory allocation representation for TDVRPDTW solution example

1 and $[e_{11}, l_{11}]$ before returning to truck 2 at node 6. In one flight, it thereby serves two customer
 2 nodes. It is important to note that the truck routes with the red shadows are currently congested.

3 Therefore, to sum up, the issue established in this article, the truck fleet consists of several
 4 trucks, each of which has a single drone. Trucks are thought to have limitless carrying capacity,
 5 whereas drones have carrying limits. Every route for the vehicles begins and finishes at the depot,
 6 and their routing problem is modeled as a VRP. As long as the capacity limit is not reached and the
 7 drone battery is not drained, each drone can visit numerous nodes in a single trip. Since the drone
 8 must synchronize with the vehicle with which it was first paired, switching the drone between two
 9 trucks is not permitted. Only at a client node are drones permitted to take off from and land in the
 10 vehicle. At the drone's landing node, the truck and drone routes are coordinated. For instance, the
 11 truck must wait for the drone if it comes before, and vice versa. The drone service should take
 12 place in a given time window for each node, as drone delivery requires manual help. Considering
 13 road congestion, a speed profile is associated with each edge. Instead of using constant travel times
 14 between each pair of nodes (i, j) in the graph, we use travel times that depend on the departure time
 15 at node i . Each node is served only once either by a truck or a drone.

16 Studies on drone deliveries show that their payload and flying time are severely constrained since
 17 the majority of drones are fueled by lithium-ion batteries, which have a low energy consumption
 18 [Zhang et al. \(2020\)](#). Thus, it is essential to incorporate drone endurance into modeling. The fleet is
 19 viewed as homogenous, and operating limitations include drone endurance modeling, which takes
 20 into account the relationship between battery capacity, power consumption speed, load weight, and

1 delivery distance. We presume the battery is completely charged without additional expense or
 2 delay before each launch of the drone. You may accomplish this by changing the battery.

3 3.2. Notations

4 The TDVRPDTW problem is defined on a complete and directed graph $G = (V, E)$, where
 5 $V = \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$ is the vertex set and $E = \{(i, j) : i, j \in V, i \neq j\}$ is the edge set. The depot is denoted
 6 by vertex 0. The set of other vertices $V^c = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is the set of n customers. Each customer is
 7 associated with a demand w_i , and a pair of time e_i, l_i , which is the earliest and latest time to service
 8 node i if the node is served by drone. If this node is served by a truck, the time window constraint is
 9 relaxed. To satisfy its demand, each customer must be visited by either truck or drone exactly once.
 10 Since the drone speed and truck speed are different, the traveling time on an arc by truck and drone
 11 are different. Furthermore, the travel time for truck to go through is time dependent. Thus, we use
 12 $\tau_{i,j}(t)$ to denote the truck's travelling time of arc (i, j) if truck leaves node i at time t . In terms of the
 13 drone's travelling time, T_{ij}^U is a given parameter which denotes the time for drone to go through arc
 14 (i, j) . For the sake of simplify, we add other nodes $n + 1, \dots, n + k$, such that each truck route will
 15 start at node 0 and ends at node $n + k$.

16 There is a fleet of homogeneous trucks $K = \{1, \dots, k\}$. Each truck is equipped with one drone and
 17 must depart and return to the single depot. The drone has a self-weight w^U and a maximum capacity
 18 of Q^U . Energy consumption is a limitation to drone flight. We adopt the energy consumption model
 19 in [Dorling et al. \(2016\)](#), in which a fixed energy consumption rate per weight per time α and the
 20 full battery capacity θ is given. Thus, if a drone traveling arc (i, j) with w payload on it, the energy
 21 consumption will be $\alpha \cdot (w^U + w) \cdot T_{(i,j)}^U$. Also, at the merging node i , the drone may hover for T^H
 22 time, which causes another $\alpha \cdot T_i^H \cdot w^U$ energy. The entire amount of energy used during a single
 23 drone flight will not be greater than the battery's *theta* maximum capacity.

24 To model the drone trips, we use a set $D = 1, 2, \dots, \lceil n/2 \rceil$ to represent possible drone trips. The
 25 size of this drone trip set is enough because for each drone trip, there is at least one unique launch
 26 node and visited node. If there are $\lceil n/2 \rceil$ drone trips, the total number of nodes are larger than n .
 27 Therefore, at most $\lceil n/2 \rceil$ drone trips exist in a solution. A drone trip $d \in D$ will be set to empty if it
 28 is not used in the solution.

1 To represent the time-dependent travel time for a truck to go through arc (i, j) , the commonly
2 used speed profile is used here. A speed profile is associated with each arc. This speed profile
3 divides the planning horizon into time zones, each with a constant speed. Using the method
4 proposed in Ichoua et al. (2003), we can have the piecewise linear function $\tau_{i,j}(t)$, which is the time
5 need for truck to go through (i, j) . Since the speed profile is adopted, travel time function $\tau_{i,j}(t)$
6 adheres to the FIFO principle. Such travel time functions do not allow passing. Since $\tau_{i,j}(t)$ is
7 piecewise linear, this function can be uniquely determined by its breakpoints $\{t_{i,j}^1, t_{i,j}^2, \dots, t_{i,j}^m\}$, and
8 the associated linear travel time function in each time interval. For the m -th interval, the slope is $\delta_{i,j}^m$
9 and the intersection is $\eta_{i,j}^m$. The time-dependent travel function can be formally written as:

$$\tau_{i,j}^m = \sum_i (\delta_{i,j}^m t + \eta_{i,j}^m) \mathbb{1}_{i,j}^m(t),$$

10 where $\mathbb{1}_{i,j}^m(t)$ equals to 1 if and only if $w_{i,j}^m - 1 \leq t < w_{i,j}^m$.

11 A summary of all notations used in this problem is displayed in Table 1.

12 3.3. Objective and Decision Variables

13 The TDVRPDTW plans a set of combined truck-drone routes to serve a set of customers to
14 minimize the total makespan of all routes, including the travel times between vehicle nodes and the
15 waiting times for drones to return to vehicle nodes. To formulate the model, decision variables are
16 defined in Table 2.

17 Regarding binary decision variables, Z_{ik}^G indicates whether the customer node i is served by
18 truck k , and if the node is served by a truck, it will be served by only one truck once. Similarly,
19 Z_i^U indicates whether customer node i is served by drone visit d . Drone visit d is a part of the
20 entire drone route, in which the drone departs from the truck and serves consumers alone, and
21 synchronizes with the truck at the end node of the visit. To represent the routes for trucks and
22 drones, y_{ij}^k and x_{ijd} are utilized. y_{ij}^k indicates whether truck k travels along arc (i, j) , solutions of
23 which show the routes arrangement in VRP. x_{ijd} indicates whether drone visit d goes through path
24 $i \rightarrow j$. Then the number of drones on the truck is represented with N_i^A, N_i^L . As each truck is
25 associated with one drone, thus if the drone launches at node i , the number of drones on the truck
26 after arriving i is 1, and the number of drones on the truck after leaving i is 0. It follows the same

Table 1: Parameter notation

Notation	Description
C	Set of customers
V	Set of all nodes $\{0, 1, \dots, n\}$
V^c	Set of all customer nodes $\{1, \dots, n\}$
E	Set of all edges
K	Set of all trucks
t_{ij}^U	Time cost when drone flies along arc $(i, j) \in E$
Q^U	The maximum weight capacity of carried packages by a drone
s_i^U	The time requested for a drone to serve customer i
s_i^G	The time requested for a truck to serve customer i
e_i	The earliest service time for a drone node
l_i	The latest service time for a drone node
w_i	The weight of the package required by customer i
w^U	The self-weight of a drone
α	Battery energy consumption rate per weight per time unit
θ	The maximum battery capacity of the drone
$M_{i,j}$	Time intervals for the piecewise linear travel time function at arc (i, j)
$t_{i,j}^m$	The m -th break point of the piecewise linear truck travel time function at arc (i, j)
$\delta_{i,j}^m$	The slope for the linear travel time function at arc (i, j) in the m -th time slot
$\eta_{i,j}^m$	The y-intercept for the linear travel time function at arc (i, j) in the m -th interval

Table 2: List of decision variables

Notation	Description
$Z_{ik}^G \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether customer i is served by truck k
$Z_{id}^U \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether customer i is served by drone visit d
$y_{ij}^k \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether truck k travels along arc $(i, j) \in E$
$x_{ijd} \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether drone visit d goes through $i \rightarrow j$
$N_i^A \in \{0, 1\}$	The number of drones on the truck after arriving i
$N_i^L \in \{0, 1\}$	The number of drones on the truck after leaving i
$h_{id}^L \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether node i is the launch node for drone visit d
$h_{id}^R \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether node i is the retrieval node for drone visit d
$I_{ijm} \in \{0, 1\}$	Indicates whether there is a truck going through $i \rightarrow j$ in the m -th time interval
$0 \leq w_i^U \leq Q^U$	The payload of the drone when leaving node i
$0 \leq \rho_i \leq \theta$	The energy of drone when leaving node j
$t_i^{UA} \geq 0$	The drone's arrival time at node i
$t_i^{GA} \geq 0$	The truck's arrival time at node i
$t_i^{GL} \geq 0$	The truck's (drone's) departure time from node i
$h_i \geq 0$	The drone's hovering time at node i

1 principle for a truck to retrieve its paired drone at node i . h_{id}^L, h_{id}^R indicate whether node i is the
 2 launch or retrieve node in the drone visit d , thus i is the starting/ending point of the drone visit. I_{ijm}
 3 means whether there is a truck going through $i \rightarrow j$ in the m -th time interval without the need to
 4 specify the truck numbering.

5 Concerning continuous variables, w_i^U captures the already carried payload of the drone when
 6 leaving node i . Then four variables are relevant for truck-drone synchronization in terms of time
 7 feasibility. t_i^{UA}, t_i^{GA} represent the drone's and the truck's arrival time at node i separately. And t_i^{GL}
 8 denotes the truck's departure time from node i , which is also the departure time for the drone if the
 9 drone returns to the truck at this node since they wait for each other. Thereafter, if the drone arrives
 10 earlier at node i than the truck for synchronization, it hovers for time h_i to wait for the truck arrival,
 11 during which energy consumption is incurred. And if the truck arrives early, there will not be the
 12 hovering time and the synchronization happens at the truck-drone leaving time.

13 3.4. Mathematical Formulation

14 A MILP model for the TDVRPDTW is presented as follows. The constraints of the model
 15 are grouped into routing constraints for trucks and drones, duration constraints with endurance
 16 modeling, and time constraints for truck-drone synchronization.

Objective function:

$$\min \sum_{k \in K} t_{n+k}^{G,L} \quad (1)$$

s.t.

Routing constraints:

$$\sum_{d \in D} Z_{id}^U + \sum_{k \in K} Z_{ik}^G = 1, \forall i \in V^c \quad (2)$$

$$Z_{0k}^G = 1, \forall k \in K \quad (3)$$

$$Z_{n+k,k}^G = 1, \forall k \in K \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} x_{jid} = Z_{id}^U + h_{id}^R, \forall i \in V, d \in D \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} Y_{jik} = Z_{ik}^G, \forall i \in V, k \in K \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{j \in V} X_{jid} + h_{id}^L = h_{id}^R + \sum_{j \in V} X_{ijd}, \forall i \in V \quad (7)$$

$$h_{id}^L \geq X_{ijd} + Z_{jd} - Z_{id} - 1, \forall i \in V, j \in V, d \in D \quad (8)$$

$$h_{jd}^R \geq X_{jid} + Z_{id} - Z_{jd} - 1, \forall i \in V, j \in V, d \in D \quad (9)$$

$$h_{id}^L + h_{id}^R \leq 1, \forall i \in V, d \in D \quad (10)$$

$$h_{id}^L \leq \sum_{k \in K} Z_{ik}, \forall i \in V \quad (11)$$

$$h_{id}^R \leq \sum_{k \in K} Z_{ik}, \forall i \in V \quad (12)$$

$$h_{id}^L + h_{jd}^R \leq 2 - Z_{ik}^G + Z_{jk}^G, \forall i \in V, j \in V, d \in D, k \in K \quad (13)$$

$$h_{id}^L + h_{jd}^R \leq 2 + Z_{ik}^G - Z_{jk}^G, \forall i \in V, j \in V, d \in D, k \in K \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{i \in V} h_{id}^R = \sum_{i \in V} h_{id}^L, \forall d \in D \quad (15)$$

Duration constraints:

$$N_j^A \leq N_i^L + \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{l \in V} X_{ljd} + (1 - \sum_{k \in K} y_{ijk}), \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (16)$$

$$N_i^L \leq N_i^A - \sum_{d \in D} \sum_{l \in V} x_{ild}, \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (17)$$

$$w_j^U + w_i \leq w_i^U + M(2 - \sum_{d \in D} x_{ijd} - \sum_{d \in D} Z_{jd}^U), \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (18)$$

$$\rho_j \leq \rho_i - \alpha(t_{ij}^U + s_j)(w_i^U + w^U) - \alpha h_j(w_j^U + w^U) + M(2 - \sum_{d \in D} x_{ijd} - \sum_{d \in D} Z_{jd}^U), \quad (19)$$

$$\forall i \in V, j \in V$$

$$\rho_j \leq \rho_i - \alpha t_{ij}^U w^U - \alpha h_j w^U + M(2 - \sum_d x_{ijd} - \sum_d H_{jd}^R), \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (20)$$

Time constraints:

$$\sum_{m \in M_{i,j}} I_{ijm} = \sum_{k \in K} y_{ij}^k, \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (21)$$

$$I_{ijm} t_{ij}^m \leq t_i^{GL} + M(1 - I_{ijm}), \forall (i, j) \in E, \forall m \in M_{i,j} \quad (22)$$

$$t_i^{GL} \leq I_{ijm} t_{ij}^{m+1} + M(1 - I_{ijm}), \forall (i, j) \in E, \forall m \in M_{i,j} \quad (23)$$

$$M(1 - I_{ijm}) + t_j^{GA} \geq t_i^{GL} + \delta_{ij}^{m, GL} t_i^{GL} + \eta_{ij}^m, \forall (i, j) \in E, \forall m \in M_{i,j} \quad (24)$$

$$t_i^{GL} \geq t_i^{GA} + s_i^G - M \left(1 - \sum_{k \in K} Z_{ik}^G \right), \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (25)$$

$$t_j^{UA} \geq t_i^{UL} + t_{ij}^U - M \left(1 - \sum_{d \in D} x_{ijd} \right), \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (26)$$

$$t_i^{UL} \geq t_i^{UA} + s_i^U - M \left(1 - \sum_{d \in D} Z_{id}^U \right), \forall i \in C \quad (27)$$

$$t_i^{UL} \geq e_i + s_i^U - M \left(1 - \sum_{d \in D} Z_{id}^U \right), \forall i \in C \quad (28)$$

$$t_i^{UA} \leq l_i + M \left(1 - \sum_{d \in D} Z_{id}^U \right), \forall i \in C \quad (29)$$

$$h_i \geq e_i - t_i^{UA} - M \left(1 - \sum_{d \in D} Z_{id}^U \right), \forall i \in C \quad (30)$$

1 The objective function (1) seeks to minimize the total makespan of all trucks. In the routing
2 constraints, constraint (2) ensures that each customer is served by either truck or drone exactly once.
3 Constraints (3) and (4) is the special case for depot. Constraint (5) ensures that if a node is served
4 by a drone or is a retrieval node of a drone visit, this node must be visited by one drone. Constraint
5 (6) ensures that customers serviced by the k -th truck must be visited by this truck. Constraint (7)
6 guarantees flow balance for each drone node.

7 Constraints (8) and (9) determine the launch node and retrieval node of the drone trip d
8 respectively. Constraint (10) ensures the retrieval node of a drone trip differs from the launch
9 node. Constraint (11) and (12) ensures that the drone can only launch and retrieve at a truck
10 node. Constraint (13) and (14) ensures that the drone must launch and retrieve at the same truck.
11 Constraint (15) ensures an equal number of launch nodes and retrieval nodes in each drone trip,
12 with at most one launch node in each drone trip.

13 In duration constraints, constraint (16) and (17) updates the number of drones onboard. Con-
14 straint (18) guarantee the feasibility on weight changes. Constraint (19) and (20) updates the energy
15 of drone. The second item in RHS of (19) is the energy needed to go through arc (i, j) , and the third
16 item is the energy needed to hover at node j . (20) is the special case when node j is the retrieval

1 node of this drone visit.

2 In time constraints, constraint (21)-(23) determines the value of I_{ijm} . Constraint (21) ensures
 3 that if a truck goes through arc (i, j) , it must go through this arc in a time interval. Constraint (22)
 4 and (23) ensures if the truck goes through arc (i, j) during $m - th$ time interval, the leaving time
 5 must lies between the left endpoint and right endpoint of this interval. Constraint (24) and (25)
 6 ensures the correctness of departure and arrival time of truck. (24) updates the arrival time of the
 7 truck at a node based on its departure time from the previous node, the time interval that departure
 8 time lies in, and the corresponding time-dependent travel time. (25) ensures the truck will not leave
 9 until the node is served.

10 Similarly, constraint (26)-(29) ensures the correctness of departure and arrival time of drone.
 11 (26) updates the arrival time of the truck at a node, and the drone's travel time is not time-dependent.
 12 (27) ensures the drone will not leave until the node is served. (28) ensures the drone will wait for
 13 until the service start time if it arrives earlier. (29) ensures the drone will not violate the latest
 14 service time constraint. Constraint (30) calculates the hovering time for drone at each node.

15 3.5. Linearized Model

16 Since h_j and w_j^U both are decision variables, constraint (19) is nonlinear. To make this model
 17 linear, we will linearize this constraint by introducing the following variables:

- 18 • ζ_{ij} : indicates whether node j is node i 's successor in one drone visit;
- 19 • ρ_{ij}^h : the hovering energy cost at node i caused by the weight carried for node j ;
- 20 • ρ_i^h : the hovering energy cost at node i .

Thus, constraint (19) is replaced by the following constraints.

$$\zeta_{ij} \geq X_{ijd} + Z_{id}^U, \forall i \in V, j \in V, d \in D \quad (31)$$

$$\zeta_{il} \geq \zeta_{jl} + X_{ijd} - 1, \forall i \in V, j \in V, l \in V, d \in D \quad (32)$$

$$\rho_{ij}^h \geq h_i w_j - M(1 - \zeta_{ij}), \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (33)$$

$$\rho_i^h \geq h_i(w_i + w^U) + \sum_{j \in V} \rho_{ij}^h, \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (34)$$

$$\rho_j \leq \rho_i - \alpha(t_{ij}^U + s_j)(w_i^U + w^U) - \rho_i^h + M(2 - \sum_{d \in D} x_{ijd} - \sum_{d \in D} Z_{jd})$$

$$, \forall i \in V, j \in V \quad (35)$$

1 Constraint (31) and (32) ensures the correctness of ζ_{ij} . Constraint (31) ensures that if there is a
 2 drone arc from i to j , j is a successor of i . Constraint (32) ensures that the successor of a successor
 3 is also a successor. Constraint (33) calculates hovering energy cost at node i caused by the weight
 4 carried for node j . Constraint (34) calculates the total hovering energy cost at node i , including cost
 5 caused by the drone's weight and package at node i , as well as cost caused by all successors of node
 6 i . Constraint (35) updates the energy of drone, which is similar to constraint (19). Thus, the MILP
 7 formulation is proposed, and the model can be solved by commercial solvers such as CPLEX.

8 4. Branch and Price Method

9 The proposed MILP model can be solved using commercial solvers, such as CPLEX or Gurobi.
 10 However, this model is too complex to solve for medium or large size instance. Thus, a branch and
 11 price based method is proposed to solve this problem more efficiently.

12 4.1. Additional Waiting Before leaving

Figure 2: Example of additional waiting before leave

13 Because of the time dependent setting, vehicle may wait longer after the node is served. For
 14 most time dependent vehicle routing problem where the objective is to minimize the total duration,
 15 a latter dispatch at depot is possible in the optimal solution, while additional waiting at other

1 customer nodes is not possible because of the FIFO principle. However, in our setting, the addition
2 waiting operation may happen at any truck node. Fig. 2 shows an example of additional waiting
3 before leaving at a truck node which is not depot. In this example, the truck's ready at node i is 0.
4 There is a drone visit i, k, j , and meanwhile the truck goes from i to j . If the truck departs at time 0,
5 because of the time window constraint, the drone has to hover at node k until the service start time,
6 which will cause addition energy cost and make the endurance constraint unsatisfied. If the truck
7 wait and depart at time 9, the drone will arrive at node k at time 10, and there will be no hovering at
8 node k , which means the energy cost for this drone route is reduced.

9 On the other hand, it is easy to show additional waiting at drone node is impossible, because the
10 drone arc has a fixed speed independent with the arrival time. Because of the FIFO principle, it
11 is also impossible to have additional waiting at truck node when this node not a launch node of a
12 drone visit.

13 For a subroute R , we use R_i to denote the i -th node in this subroute. Truck's arrival time at
14 the i -th node is a piecewise linear function of leaving time, denoted as $T_i^{AG,R}(t)$. This function can
15 be determined using method proposed in [Dabia et al. \(2013\)](#). This method can be easily applied
16 to a drone subroute, and the drone's arrival time is also a piecewise linear function, denoted as
17 $T_i^{AU,R}(t)$. Furthermore, we use R_{-1} to denote the last node in this route. Given drone subroute R^D ,
18 truck subroute R^T ($R_1^D = R_1^T$, $R_{-1}^D = R_{-1}^T$) and the ready time t_0 at R_1^T , the energy drone needs to
19 finish R^D is a function of leaving time $Q(t)$. $Q(t)$ consists of two parts:

- 20 1. $Q_1(t)$: energy need for the drone visit ;
- 21 2. $Q_2(t)$:energy need for hovering at R_{-1}^D .

22 Apparently, $Q_2(t) = \max\{0, T_{-1}^{AG,R^T}(t) - T_{-1}^{AU,R^D}(t)\} \cdot w^U \cdot \alpha$ is a piecewise linear function.

23 In order to determine $Q_1(t)$, the example of R^D, R^T is shown in Fig. 3(a). If the drone is launched
24 at time t_0 , the time at it arrives at each node is shown in Fig. 3(b). For node 2, the drone will
25 arrive earlier than the service start time. Thus, if the drone is launched latter, the hovering time
26 at node 2 is reduced. As a result, $Q_1(t)$ is also a piecewise linear function. This function can be
27 uniquely determined by all the breakpoints and corresponding values. The first breakpoint is t_0 and
28 correspond value is E_0 . Because of the time window constraint in each node, there is a upper bound

Figure 3: Explanation diagram of algorithm

- 1 for the leaving time, denoted as \bar{T} . Algorithm 1 is used to determine these breakpoints and \bar{T} .

Algorithm 1 Algorithm to determine Q_1 and \bar{T}

Input

R^D : drone subroute;

R^T : truck subroute;

t_0 : ready time at R_1^T

Output

BP : list of breakpoints;

V : list of function value at each breakpoint;

\bar{T} : upper bound for leaving time

Procedure

- 1: $\bar{T} = \inf, T = t_0$
 - 2: $BP = [t_0], V = [E_0]$
 - 3: w is the total weight of package carried in R^D
 - 4: **for** i from 2 to $|R^D|$ **do**
 - 5: $T = T + t_{i-1,i}^U$
 - 6: $\bar{T} = \min\{\bar{T}, BP_{-1} + l_i - T\}$
 - 7: **if** $T < e_i$ **then**
 - 8: $BP.append(BP_{-1} + e_i - T)$
 - 9: $V.append(V_{-1} - \alpha w e_i - T)$
 - 10: $T = e_i$
 - 11: **end if** $T = T + s_i w = w - w_i$
 - 12: **end for**
 - 13: **return** BP, V, \bar{T}
-

- 2 Now, we can simply compute the leaving time at R_1^T by solving the following problem:

$$\min \{t : Q(t) \leq \theta; t_0 \leq t \leq \bar{t}\}. \quad (\text{P1})$$

1 Since $Q(t)$ is a piecewise linear function, we can check each linear intervals one after another
 2 until we found the minimal t . If we still cannot find a feasible t after the last interval is checked,
 3 this truck route and drone route is not feasible.

4 4.2. Master Problem

5 The following notations are introduced to construct the master problem:

- 6 • Ω : the set of all feasible routes;
- 7 • c_p : the cost (total time) of a feasible route p ;
- 8 • δ_{ip} : the number of times that node i is visited in route p ;
- 9 • y_p binary variable that takes 1 if and only if route p is selected.

Thus, the TDVRPDTW problem can be formulated as the following set partitioning problem:

$$\text{sum} \sum_{p \in \Omega} c_p y_p \quad (36)$$

$$s.t. \quad (37)$$

$$\sum_{p \in \Omega} \delta_{ip} y_p = 1 \quad \forall i \in V \quad (38)$$

$$\sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \leq k \quad (39)$$

$$y_p \in [0, 1] \quad \forall p \in \Omega \quad (40)$$

10 The objective function (1) minimizes the total time used. Constraint (2) force each node to be
 11 visited once. Constraint (3) is the truck number constraint. Constraint (4) is the domain for binary
 12 variables.

13 The set of all feasible routes Ω is very large. As a result, a column generation approach is
 14 proposed. The initial set of feasible routes is constructed by greedy insertion of all nodes into

1 k truck routes. Let $\pi_i, i \in V$ be the dual variable for each node corresponding to constraint (38),
2 and π' be the dual variable corresponding to constraint (39). The reduced cost of a route r is
3 $\bar{c}_r = c_r - \sum_{i \in V} \delta_{ir} \pi_i - \pi'$.

4 4.3. Branching Strategy

5 A best-bound strategy is used to explore the branch-and-price tree. To branch on relaxed
6 variables, the following methods are adopted in order.

- 7 • Branch on truck arc: Let κ_{ijp} indicates whether arc (i, j) is visited by truck in path p . We will
8 look for an arc (i^*, j^*) such that $\sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \kappa_{i^* j^* p}$ is the closest to 0.5 and imposes two branches
9 $\sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \kappa_{i^* j^* p} \leq \lfloor \sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \kappa_{i^* j^* p} \rfloor$ and $\sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \kappa_{i^* j^* p} \leq \lceil \sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \kappa_{i^* j^* p} \rceil$
- 10 • Branch on drone arc: Let μ_{ijp} indicates whether arc (i, j) is visited by drone in path p . We will
11 look for an arc (i^*, j^*) such that $\sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \mu_{i^* j^* p}$ is the closest to 0.5 and imposes two branches
12 $\sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \mu_{i^* j^* p} \leq \lfloor \sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \mu_{i^* j^* p} \rfloor$ and $\sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \mu_{i^* j^* p} \leq \lceil \sum_{p \in \Omega} y_p \mu_{i^* j^* p} \rceil$

13 4.4. Pricing Problem

14 The pricing problem is to find a feasible route with negative reduced cost. We propose a labeling
15 algorithm to solve this problem, where the labels are extended from depot to its successors. A label
16 L is defined as:

- 17 • $v(L)$: the last truck node where a drone can launch;
- 18 • $t_0(L)$: the earliest departure time for node v ;
- 19 • $R_D(L)$: the drone subroute from node v ;
- 20 • $R_T(L)$: the truck subroute from node v ;
- 21 • $S(L)$: the set of nodes visited in this label;
- 22 • $c(L)$: the accumulated dual value of the label.

23 The initial label is $(0, 0, [], [], \emptyset, 0)$. Given a label, the following labels can be created by add
24 new nodes to the end of this path. The new nodes can be added into the drone subroute or truck
25 subroute, or this new node is a truck route and will be added into the end of this path.

26 **Case 1.** For the existing label L' , if R_D and R_T is empty, and there is an unvisited node u , the
27 following new label L will be created.

- 1 • $v(L) = u$;
- 2 • $t_0(L) = t_0(L') + \tau_{v(L'),u}(t_0(L'))$;
- 3 • $R_D = []$;
- 4 • $R_T = []$;
- 5 • $S(L) = S(L') \cup \{u\}$;
- 6 • $c(L) = c(L') + \pi_u$.

7 **Case 2.** For the existing label L' , if R_D and R_T is empty, and there is a pair of unvisited nodes
8 u_1, u_2 , such that drone route $[v(L'), u_1]$ and truck route $[v(L'), u_2]$ is feasible correspond to problem
9 **P1**, the following new label L will be created.

- 10 • $v(L) = v(L')$;
- 11 • $t_0(L) = t_0(L')$;
- 12 • $R_D = [v(L'), u_1]$;
- 13 • $R_T = [v(L'), u_2]$;
- 14 • $S(L) = S(L') \cup \{u_1, u_2\}$;
- 15 • $c(L) = c(L') + \pi_{u_1} + \pi_{u_2}$.

16 **Case 3.** For the existing label L' , if R_D and R_T is not empty, and there is an unvisited nodes
17 u , such that drone route $R_D + u$ and truck route R_T is feasible corresponding to problem **P1**, the
18 following new label L will be created.

- 19 • $v(L) = v(L')$;
- 20 • $t_0(L) = t_0(L')$;
- 21 • $R_D = R_D + u$;
- 22 • $R_T = R_T$;
- 23 • $S(L) = S(L') \cup \{u\}$;
- 24 • $c(L) = c(L') + \pi_u$.

25 **Case 4.** For the existing label L' , if R_D and R_T is not empty, and there is an unvisited nodes
26 u , such that drone route R_D and truck route $R_T + u$ is feasible corresponding to problem **P1**, the
27 following new label L will be created.

- 1 • $v(L) = v(L')$;
- 2 • $t_0(L) = t_0(L')$;
- 3 • $R_D = R_D$;
- 4 • $R_T = R_T + u$;
- 5 • $S(L) = S(L') \cup \{u\}$;
- 6 • $c(L) = c(L') + \pi_u$.

7 **Case 5.** For the existing label L' , if L_D and L_T is not empty, the following new label L will be
8 created. Let t' be the computed leaving time for L_D and L_T .

- 9 • $v(L) = R_T(L')_{-1}$;
- 10 • $t(L)$ =time of ready time at $R_T(L')_{-1}$ when depaurte time at $R_T(L')_0$ is t' ;
- 11 • $R_D = []$;
- 12 • $R_T = []$;
- 13 • $S(L) = S(L')$;
- 14 • $c(L) = c(L')$.

15 Given a label, we will generate all possible extended labels. We note that above 5 cases for
16 creating is complete, meaning for each the feasible route can be generated, if the triangle inequality
17 holds and speed of drone is always larger than truck. For most of the cases in real world, the triangle
18 inequality holds, and drone travels faster than truck.

19 **Theorem 1.** *All the feasible routes will be created during the labeling procedure if triangle*
20 *inequality holds and speed of drone is always larger than truck.*

21 *Proof.* We will proof by contradiction. Suppose there is a feasible route L which cannot be created
22 during the labeling procedure. Starting from the initial label, if there is a extended label which
23 forms a partial route of R , we will update the current label to this extended label. This procedure
24 will stop when we have a label L_0 which represents a partial route of R , and all its extended label
25 does not forms a partial route of R .

26 If $R^D(L_0) = R^T(L_0) = []$, and the immediate successor of $v(L_0)$ in L is a truck node, we can
27 create another label by selecting this immediate successor as node u in case 1.

1 If $R^D(L_0)$ and $R^T(L_0)$ are not empty, and the immediate successors of $R^D(L_0)_{-1}$ is $R^T(L_0)_{-1}$, we
 2 can create another label from this label in case 3.

3 For the remaining cases, in order to generate the new label, we must extend the drone route or
 4 truck route. Since this new label cannot be generated from current label, we know that there is
 5 a node u such that u is the successor of $R^D(L_0)$ or $R^T(L_0)$, and the subroutes with u is infeasible
 6 corresponding to problem P1. We will show that this is impossible. Denote the subroutes with u
 7 inserted as R_1^D, R_1^T . The subroutes in L is denoted as R_2^D, R_2^T . Noted that R_1^D and R_1^T are prefixes of R_2^D
 8 and R_2^T , and problem P1 corresponding to R_2^D and R_2^T is feasible while problem P1 corresponding to
 9 R_1^D and R_2^T is infeasible. However, this is impossible. Suppose in L , the departure time of first node
 10 in R_2^T is t_0 . Thus, if the time that drone launches at first node in R_1^T is t_0 , we have $Q_1(R_1^D) \leq Q_1(R_2^D)$,
 11 because the payload in R_1^D is less than or equal to R_2^D . In terms of Q_2 , since the triangle inequality
 12 holds, and drone travels faster, the time that drone flies with no package in R_1^D is smaller than in
 13 R_2^D . □

14 During the labeling procedure, all the labels are derived and stored, which leads to a large
 15 number of labels. We will ignore the label L' if it is dominated by some other label, and thus the
 16 searching space is reduced. For a given label L , let $E(L)$ to be the set of extension of L , which
 17 means any route in $E(L)$ can start from L and ends at $n + 1$ without violating any constraint.

18 We say a label L_1 dominates L_2 , denoted as $L_1 < L_2$, if all the feasible extension for L_2 is also
 19 feasible for L_1 and for any feasible extension L , reduced cost of L_1 is always better than L_2 . Formally,
 20 $L_1 < L_2$ if :

- 21 • $E(L_2) \subseteq E(L_1)$;
- 22 • $c(L_1 + L) \geq c(L_2 + L)$, $\forall L \in E(L_2)$

23 In order to check whether a label is dominated by another in a short time, the following
 24 dominance rules are used.

25 **Proposition 1.** *Given two labels L_1 and L_2 , $L_1 < L_2$ if the following holds:*

- 26 • $L_D(L_1) = L_D(L_2) = []$
- 27 • $L_T(L_1) = L_T(L_2) = []$

- 1 • $t(L_1) \leq t(L_2)$
- 2 • $v(L_1) = v(L_2)$
- 3 • $c(L_1) \leq c(L_2)$
- 4 • $s(L_1) \subseteq s(L_2)$

5 *Proof.* First, we will prove that any feasible extension for L_2 is also feasible for L_1 . Suppose there
6 is a $L \in E(L_2)$, the departure time at node $v(L_2)$ in route $L_2 + L$ is larger than $t(L_2)$, and thus larger
7 than $t(L_1)$. Thus, for $L_1 + L$, the truck can wait at $v(L_1)$ and $L_1 + L$ will not violate any time window
8 constraint or endurance constraint. Furthermore, since $s(L_1) \subseteq s(L_2)$, $L_1 + L$ is also a feasible route.
9 Since truck waits at $v(L_1)$ in route $L_1 + L$, the total time to finish route $L_1 + L$ is small than or equal
10 to $L_2 + L$. The reduced cost is thus smaller. \square

11 **Proposition 2.** Given two labels L_1 and L_2 . Consider the problem *P1* corresponding to L_1 and
12 L_2 , which gives $\bar{t}(L_1)$ and $\bar{t}(L_2)$, as well as energy cost function $Q_1(t, L_1)$ and $Q_1(t, L_2)$. Also, let
13 $T_i^{AG,R}(t, L)$ and $T_i^{AU,R}(t, L)$ be the arrival time at i -th node in the truck/drone subroute in partial
14 route represented in label L . Let $W(L)$ be all the weights of package carried in $R^D(L)$. $L_1 < L_2$ if
15 the following holds:

- 16 • $R_D(L_1)_{-1} = R_D(L_2)_{-1}$;
- 17 • $R_T(L_1)_{-1} = R_T(L_2)_{-1}$;
- 18 • $s(L_1) \subseteq s(L_2)$;
- 19 • $c(L_1) \leq c(L_2)$;
- 20 • $t_0(L_1) \leq t_0(L_2)$;
- 21 • $\bar{t}(L_1) \geq \bar{t}(L_2)$;
- 22 • $T_{-1}^{AG,R}(t, L_1) \leq T_{-1}^{AG,R}(t, L_2), \forall t \in [t, \bar{t}]$;
- 23 • $T_{-1}^{AU,R}(t, L_1) \leq T_{-1}^{AU,R}(t, L_2), \forall t \in [t, \bar{t}]$;
- 24 • $Q_1(t, L_1) + \alpha(T_{-1}^{AU,R}(t, L_2) - T_{-1}^{AU,R}(t, L_1))(\theta - W(L)) \leq Q_1(t, L_2), \forall t \in [t, \bar{t}]$

25 *Proof.* For any extension L which is feasible for L_2 , we will prove that constraints in problem *P1*
26 corresponding to $L_1 + L$ is also feasible. $Q(t, L_1) = Q_1(t, L_1) + Q_2(t, L_1)$. Suppose departure time
27 at $R_1^T(L_2)$ in $L_2 + L$ is t . If drone launches at time t in $L_1 + L$, since $T_{-1}^{AG,R}(t, L_1) \leq T_{-1}^{AG,R}(t, L_2)$,

1 the truck's arrival time is smaller in $L_1 + L$. Let drone wait for $T_{-1}^{AU,R}(t, L_2) - T_{-1}^{AU,R}(t, L_1)$ at
2 node $R_{-1}^D(L_1)$, and then following the same schedule in $L_2 + L$. As a result, the hovering time at
3 retrieval node is smaller in $L_1 + L$, which leads to the smaller energy cost after $R_{-1}^D(L_1)$ is smaller in
4 $L_1 + L$. However, hovering at node $R_{-1}^D(L_1)$ leads to additional energy cost. This cost is bounded by
5 $\alpha(T_{-1}^{AU,R}(t, L_2) - T_{-1}^{AU,R}(t, L_1))(\theta - W(L))$. In total, the energy cost of $L_1 + L$ is smaller when launch
6 time is t , which means L is also a feasible extension for L_1 .

7 Also, since t is a feasible solution for problem P1 corresponding to $L_1 + L$, we know that c_{L_1+L}
8 is smaller. Thus, $L_1 + L$ leads to a better reduced cost. \square

9 4.5. Heatmap Based Acceleration

10 The labeling algorithm in pricing problem is time-consuming. Even though the dominance rules
11 are applied, there are still a lot of labels generated. To reduce the number of labels generated in
12 each extension procedure, a heatmap based acceleration technique is used here. In the heatmap,
13 each arc in this graph is assigned with a probability, which mean how likely a truck will go through
14 this arc. To generate the heatmap, we use the same method proposed in Fu et al. (2021), where the
15 size of pre-trained graph is 10 and the label on each arc equals to 1 if and only if this arc belongs to
16 TSP solution or is a truck arc in our solution. For an instance with more than 30 nodes, the sample
17 method proposed in Fu et al. (2021) will be used to generate the heatmap. Based on the heatmap,
18 we will order all the arcs based on their probability, and only first 30 of the arcs will be kept. This
19 leads to a sparse graph and labeling algorithm on this sparse graph is very fast. If the route with
20 negative reduced cost is not found on the sparse graph, we will run the labeling algorithm on the
21 original graph again.

22 5. Computational Experiments

23 In this section, we present the results of a series of experiments to examine the performance
24 of the proposed branch and price algorithm. Code was implemented in Python3.10 and run on
25 a Ubuntu 18.04.3 LTS server with Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4216 CPU at 2.10 GHz and CPLEX
26 12.8.0 installed.

We first describe the newly generated test instances for the TDVRPDTW in section 5.1. The detailed experimental is provided following. Then, test instances with small, medium and large scales are solved respectively in section 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4.

5.1. Test Instances

The new test instances are generated from the widely used Solomon instance (Solomon (1987)). When a data instance with size n is generated, we first randomly select an instance from the Solomon instance, then n nodes are selected randomly to generate such a small data instance. In this work, we generated 3 different data sets with 10, 15, and 30 customers (labeled as T-10, T-15, and T-30).

In all test instances, the speed of the drone is fixed to be 2. For the drone endurance model, we set $Q = 200$, $\theta = 16000$, $\alpha = 1$, $w^U = 1$.

In terms of truck speed, since the travel time of a truck is time-dependent, the approach to model this time-dependent feature is similar to Dabia et al. (2013). There are 3 different speed profiles: slow, fast, and normal, which represent roads in the city center, highways, and roads that link highways and the city center in the real world. The whole time horizon is divided into 5 time zones, each with a different speed, meaning the peak and off-peak hours in the real world. For each arc, a speed profile is randomly assigned. The detailed information is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Speed profiles

	$Zone_1$	$Zone_2$	$Zone_3$	$Zone_4$	$Zone_5$
Time	$[0, 0.2l_0]$	$[0.2l_0, 0.3l_0]$	$[0.3l_0, 0.7l_0]$	$[0.7l_0, 0.8l_0]$	$[0.8l_0, l_0]$
Fast	1.5	1	1.67	1.17	1.33
Normal	1.17	0.67	1.33	0.83	1
Slow	1	0.33	0.67	0.5	0.83

5.2. Performance Analysis on Small Scale Instances

In this section, test instance T-10 is solved both by CPLEX and our branch and price algorithm. In this experiment, the number of available vehicles is set to 2. The result is reported in Table 4, where column Δ measures the difference between the best feasible solution found by CPLEX and PS-ALNS method. Formally, for an instance, LB and UB denotes the lower bound and upper bound

1 from CPLEX, c_{best} is the optimal solution from our branch and price algorithm, and the value in
 2 column Δ is $\frac{c_{best}-UB}{UB} \times 100\%$.

3 As shown in this result, both CPLEX and our algorithm can solve the problem with small size
 4 optimally. However, our algorithm is more efficient. The Branch and price algorithm solves each
 5 instance with an average time cost of 3.4s. However, the average computation time for CPLEX is
 6 82.8s.

Table 4: Results of numerical experiments for T-10 from two algorithms

S/N	cplex				B&P			Δ
	LB	UB	CPU time	Gap	Obj	CPU time	Opt?	
T-10-1	1159.1	1159.1	150.6/s	0	1159.1	1.2/s	✓	0%
T-10-2	984.4	984.4	77.5/s	0	984.4	3.2/s	✓	0%
T-10-3	1080.6	1080.6	57.7/s	0	1080.6	4.7/s	✓	0%
T-10-4	1021.4	1021.4	39.4/s	0	1021.4	4.8/s	✓	0%
T-10-5	1085.0	1085.0	22.3/s	0	1085.0	6.9/s	✓	0%
T-10-6	1244.1	1244.1	93.7/s	0	1244.1	6.4/s	✓	0%
T-10-7	1261.7	1261.7	197.5/s	0	1261.7	0.1/s	✓	0%
T-10-8	1256.0	1256.0	53.5/s	0	1256.0	0.8/s	✓	0%
T-10-9	1095.0	1095.0	20.7/s	0	1095.0	2.3/s	✓	0%
T-10-10	1206.8	1206.8	115.2/s	0	1206.8	4.2/s	✓	0%

7
 8 *5.3. Performance Analysis on Medium Scale Instances*

9 In this section, test instance T-15 is solved both by CPLEX and our branch and price algorithm.
 10 In this experiment, the number of available vehicles is set to 2. The result is reported in Table 5.
 11 We also set the time limit of CPLEX to 1 hour.

12 As shown in this result, CPLEX cannot solve any instance optimally within 1 hour and the
 13 average gap is 17.2%. However, our algorithm can still solve all the instances with an average
 14 computation time of 7.7s. Also, CPLEX found the optimal solution for one instance but failed to
 15 find the corresponding lower bound and prove its optimality.

Table 5: Results of numerical experiments for T-15 from two algorithms

S/N	cplex				B&P			Δ
	LB	UB	CPU time	Gap	Obj	CPU time	Opt?	
T-10-1	1039.9	1440.6	3600/s	27.8%	1133.1	6.8/s	✓	-21.3%
T-10-2	1457.8	1695.9	3600/s	14.0%	1466.1	4.1/s	✓	-13.5%
T-10-3	1445.9	1840.8	3600/s	21.4%	1722.7	9.5/s	✓	-6.4%
T-10-4	1339.8	1539.8	3600/s	13.8%	1539.8	6.2/s	✓	0%
T-10-5	1393.9	1731.6	3600/s	19.5%	1521.8	4.6/s	✓	-12.1%
T-10-6	1461.6	1691.1	3600/s	13.5%	1540.1	12.2/s	✓	-8.9%
T-10-7	1387.5	1593.7	3600/s	12.9%	1483.3	11.5/s	✓	-6.9%
T-10-8	1257.0	1463.2	3600/s	14.0%	1323.0	10.5/s	✓	-9.5%
T-10-9	1468.5	1879.5	3600/s	21.8%	1490.1	6.1/s	✓	-20.7%
T-10-10	1331.0	1531.0	3600/s	13.1%	1400.2	6.0/s	✓	-8.6%

1

2 5.4. Performance Analysis on Medium Scale Instances

3 For each test instance in data set T-30, the branch and price algorithm is used to solve the
4 corresponding problem with $k = 2, 3, 5$, meaning there are 2, 3, 5 vehicles available. To better
5 evaluate our algorithm, we set the time limit to 1 hour. The result is shown in table 6 and can be used
6 as a benchmark reference for future studies. As shown in this result, we notice with more vehicles
7 in use, the total cost will be reduced. We also notice that with a larger k , the time consuming for
8 each instance is smaller. This may because a larger k means a shorter path in each vehicle, and thus
9 the labeling procedure will be more efficient.

10

11 6. Conclusions

12 The ongoing epidemic and growing expansion of e-commerce in recent years have increased the
13 demand for last-mile delivery with better requirements of service quality. Drones are a promising
14 solution for such challenging delivery issues. In real life, traffic networks are subject to congestion,
15 and therefore travel times are time-dependent. In this paper, we capture traffic congestion due

Table 6: Results of numerical experiments for T-30

S/N	k=2			k=3			k=5		
	C_{best}	CPU time	Opt?	C_{best}	CPU time	Opt?	C_{best}	CPU time	Opt?
T-30-1	3012.3	3013/s	✓	2059.1	2372/s	✓	1399.4	2279/s	✓
T-30-2	2534.3	3302/s	✓	2287.4	2792/s	✓	1983.9	1580/s	✓
T-30-3	2902.5	2041/s	✓	2892.8	1804/s	✓	2055.7	1737/s	✓
T-30-4	2163.3	3457/s	✓	2150.0	2700/s	✓	1333.4	2262/s	✓
T-30-5	2605.3	3449/s	✓	2250.0	2987/s	✓	2178.7	2837/s	✓
T-30-6	2583.8	3600/s	×	2024.3	2430/s	✓	1786.6	1493/s	✓
T-30-7	2735.9	3514/s	✓	2359.1	3108/s	✓	2259.4	2408/s	✓
T-30-8	2903.4	2465/s	✓	2142.2	2239/s	✓	1907.1	1460/s	✓
T-30-9	2831.8	3600/s	×	2694.9	2576/s	✓	2631.1	2353/s	✓
T-30-10	2812.2	2982/s	✓	2782.2	2387/s	✓	2102.8	1763/s	✓

1 to predictable traffic density, by assuming that vehicles travel at different speeds throughout the
2 planning horizon. In our context, we introduce the time-dependent vehicle routing problem with
3 drones and time windows. When dealing with the TDVRPDTW, several challenging factors arise.
4 On the one hand, dispatch times at the depot and the order in which clients are visited affect the best
5 course of action. However, because the connection between two geographically adjacent clients
6 might appear to be a lengthy link when traveled during a busy moment, insights into the structure
7 of the instances are lost.

8 A MILP model is formulated for the problem, for which commercial solvers can only solve for
9 small-size instances. To tackle medium and large-size instances which are more practical for real-
10 world scenarios, we present the first exact algorithm for solving the TDVRPDTW. Considering time-
11 dependent travel times increases the complexity of the pricing problem and standard dominance tests
12 are not applicable. We introduce a new and stronger dominance criterion allowing the domination
13 of more labels. For a homogeneous fleet of vehicles outfitted with a single drone apiece, capable of
14 serving many clients in a single trip, the solutions identify the least travel time of all routes.

15 A new test instances data set is derived from Solomon’s data to validate the performance of the
16 proposed branch-and-price algorithm. Computational results showed that some instances with up
17 to 30 customers can be solved to optimality but also that several instances with only 30 customers
18 remain unsolved. Our computational results show great potential in cost reduction with drone

1 multi-visits. We see a myriad of opportunities for future research in this area. Potential studies may
2 explore multi-objective optimization.

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